

VISUAL DATA REPRESENTATION: RECENT ACHIEVEMENTS AND FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS

Fernando Pereira

Instituto Superior Técnico/Instituto de Telecomunicações
Av. Rovisco Pais, 1049-001 Lisboa, Portugal

Tel: + 351 21 8418460; Fax: 351 21 8418472
E-mail: fernando.pereira@lx.it.pt

ABSTRACT

This paper reviews the recent achievements and the future developments in the area of visual data representation with special emphasis on standards. Reference will be made to the MPEG-4, H.26L, JPEG 2000 and MPEG-7 ongoing activities. Moreover this paper discusses the research topics and trends which should deserve major attention after the recent and emerging milestones in terms of visual data representation technology and standards.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the last two decades, digital visual representation has been one of the most active research fields in the area of information technology. This activity led to a very significant development of tools, notably for image and video coding, and international coding standards, and finally to the widespread deployment of digital multimedia applications. Due to the interoperability requirements typical of most multimedia applications, international standards have played a major role not only in the deployment of new applications but also in giving targets and references to the scientific community, accelerating the achievements. The JPEG, H.261, MPEG-1, MPEG-2 and H.263 standards are the members of a generation of coding standards where image and video information is modelled according to a frame-based approach and coded using DCT-based hybrid coding schemes. These standards cover a wide range of applications, from photographic images and videotelephony to high quality digital TV, exploring bitrates from a few tens of kbit/s up to many tens of Mbit/s. But since digital frame-based video is just the digital translation of a data model solution constrained by the analogue world, time has arrived for more powerful and flexible visual data model approaches.

2 RECENT ACHIEVEMENTS: THE MPEG-4 MILESTONE

Recognising that audiovisual content should be created and represented using a framework that is able to give the user as many as possible real-world like capabilities, such as interaction and manipulation,

MPEG decided, in 1993, to launch a new project, well known as MPEG-4 [1]. Since human beings do not want to interact with abstract entities, such as pixels, but rather with meaningful entities that are part of the scene, the concept of object is central to MPEG-4. MPEG-4 models an audiovisual scene as a composition of audiovisual objects with specific characteristics and behaviour, notably in space and time. The object composition approach allows to support new functionalities, such as object-based interaction, manipulation and hyperlinking, as well as to improve already available functionalities, such as coding efficiency by just using for each type of object the most adequate coding tools and parameters.

One of the most exciting and powerful consequences of the object-based approach is the integration of natural and synthetic content. While until now the natural and synthetic audiovisual worlds have evolved quite in parallel, the MPEG-4 representation approach allows the composition of natural and synthetic data in the same scene, unifying the two, until now separate, worlds. This unification allows to efficiently code natural as well as synthetic visual data, without undue translations like the conversion to pixel based representations of synthetic models. Since MPEG-4 considers visual objects of various types, e.g. rectangular frames, 2D arbitrarily shaped video objects, text, graphics, 3D faces and bodies, generic 3D objects, as well as audio objects of various types, e.g. music, speech, structured audio, it is necessary not only to consider the coded representations of the various audiovisual objects but also some information describing the way by which the various objects are composed to build the final scene. The MPEG-4 data modelling approach is bitrate independent, and thus applications ranging from very low bitrate mobile videotelephony to high quality studio production are addressed.

The MPEG-4 Version 1 standards - Systems, Visual, Audio and DMIF - reached the International Standard status during the first half of 1999. Next MPEG-4 Versions will add to Version 1 some new technologies, addressing additional requirements and functionalities, e.g. generic 3D coding was finished by the end of

1999. Due to its powerful object-based approach, the use of the most efficient coding techniques, and the large variety of data types that it incorporates, MPEG-4 represents today the state-of-the-art in terms of visual data coding technology. Moreover, the analysis of the current research work on image and video coding does not allow to foresee significant developments in this area for the next years since no conceptual or technological novelties seem to be around (see H.26L [2]). This situation leads to the conclusion that MPEG-4 will represent for quite some years the top of visual coding technology and that no effort on additional audiovisual coding standards will be invested by MPEG in the next years.

Although conceptually and technologically MPEG-4 is very advanced, it is difficult to foresee if it will be a success in terms of products and applications. First of all, the effort to make MPEG-4 very complete, notably in terms of data types, transformed it in a rather big and complex standard. MPEG tried to overcome this problem through the specification of profiles and levels addressing various application classes but it is still not clear if this solution will achieve the desired results. Second, the solution of the problems related to the protection of intellectual property, both of patents and content, may prevent its large deployment, at least in a timely way to overcome emerging proprietary systems. The success of MPEG-4 may depend on the quick deployment of interactive applications on the Internet, as a first step for conquering other application environments, and on the solution of the intellectual property protection problems, notably taking into account the new application paradigms and business models addressed by MPEG-4. Whatever will be the success of the MPEG-4 standard in terms of products, determined by industrial, economical and marketing interests, the new principles and concepts used go in the right direction since they deeply rely on basic characteristics of the human-world relation, brought now to the audiovisual representation arena.

3 NEAR FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS: THE MPEG-7 CHALLENGE

While MPEG-4 Version 1 is now finished, there are still a few standardisation efforts going on. These processes will lead to some new standards or extensions to standards in the near future, addressing requirements and needs not yet considered by the current set of available standards.

Although MPEG-4 Version 1 already addressed the specific needs of mobile environments, notably error resilience and very low bitrates, making MPEG-4 the standard which best fits mobile applications needs, the same did not happen for the Internet. The growing importance of Internet applications, notably Internet video streaming, led to the development of a video coding method that is able to provide fine granularity

scalability (FGS) in video quality and temporal resolution [3]. Fine granularity scalability is a type of scalability where an enhancement layer can be truncated into any number of bits still providing a corresponding quality enhancement. This feature is important in the Internet where the bandwidth constantly varies and it is important to exploit in the best possible way the bandwidth available at each instant. The MPEG-4 FGS technology was ready at the Spring of 2000, completing the set of MPEG-4 tools addressing Internet multimedia applications. This technology is important also because it is largely expected that the Internet will play a major role in the explosion of MPEG-4 applications before more 'difficult' environments, such as broadcasting, adopt this standard.

Another activity that is under consideration in the context of MPEG-4, following the work for studio environments, is digital cinema. Digital cinema requirements include high quality (equal to or better quality than film provides today) lossy and lossless video compression as well as powerful transcoding capabilities allowing creating multiple versions of the same content depending on the relevant target.

Finally, to complete and improve its capabilities in terms of synthetic content, MPEG-4 is working towards a generic animation framework of synthetic objects including very efficient coding mechanisms, based on a high level representation of the models and animations.

But other relevant standardisation efforts beside MPEG-4 are under development. After many years of success with the JPEG standard, the JPEG experts have finalised the specification of the next still images coding standard: JPEG 2000. This standard is intended to create a new image coding system for different types of still images (bi-level, gray-level, colour, multi-component) with different characteristics (natural images, scientific, medical, remote sensing imagery, text, rendered graphics, etc.) allowing different imaging models (client/server, real-time transmission, image library archival, limited buffer and bandwidth resources, etc.) preferably within a unified system [4]. This coding system is intended to provide low bit-rate operation with rate-distortion and subjective image quality performance superior to existing standards, without sacrificing performance at other points in the rate-distortion spectrum. In addition, this system could include many advanced features such as MPEG-4 like object-based functionalities. The standard will strive for openness and royalty-free licensing [4] to avoid the complex problems faced by MPEG-4. It will be completed by the end of the millennium and offer state-of-the-art compression for at least ten years and beyond [4]. JPEG 2000 is based on wavelet technology providing a number of benefits over the previous DCT-

based JPEG standard, notably improved compression, spatial and quality scalability at fine granularity, and the definition of regions of interest [5]. Together with the MPEG-4 visual texture coding tool, this is the first time that non DCT-based technology is used for texture coding in an international image/video coding standard.

After the success of H.263, ITU-T Study Group 16 kept working on improving DCT-based hybrid coding schemes and issued two H.263 revisions – H.263+ and H.263++ - adding more functionality as well as incorporating coding efficiency improvements to H.263. Currently, SG16 believes that there is still a potential need for a new video coding algorithm capable of delivering much improved video quality and covering functionalities not supported by existing standards (e.g. H.261, H.262, H.263/the revisions of H.263, MPEG-4). Accordingly, SG16 has initiated a new video coding standardisation activity, named H.26L, which targets these areas. Since the H.26L Test Model Long Term states at its very beginning “*This document is a description of a reference coding method to be used for the development of a new compression method ITU-T recommendation- H.26L. The basic configuration of the algorithm is similar to H.263.*” [2], it is clear that for the moment no major novelties should be expected. At most, refinements similar to those introduced in H.263+ and H.263++ can be anticipated.

While the future developments mentioned above still fall under the category of image and visual coding for visualisation, the most recent MPEG standardisation effort - MPEG-7 - addresses a conceptually different problem: audiovisual content description [6]. In fact digital audiovisual information is nowadays more and more accessible to everybody, not only in terms of consumption but increasingly more also in terms of production. But if it is today easier and easier to acquire, process, and distribute audiovisual content, it must also be equally easy to access the available information, because huge amounts of audiovisual information are being generated, all over the world, every day. The need of a powerful solution for quickly and efficiently identifying (searching, filtering, etc.) various types of audiovisual content of interest to the user (human or machine), using also non text-based technologies, directly follows from the urge to efficiently use the available audiovisual content and the difficulty of doing so. MPEG-7 will specify a standard way of describing various types of audiovisual information, including still pictures, video, speech, audio, graphics, 3D models, and synthetic audio, irrespective of its representation format, e.g. analogue or digital, and storage support, e.g. paper, film or tape. In comparison with other available or emerging solutions for audiovisual content description, MPEG-7 can be mainly distinguished by: i) its *genericity* this

means its capability to describe content from many application environments; ii) its *object-based data model* this means the capability of independently describing individual objects within a scene (be it MPEG-4 or any other format); iii) the *integration of low-level and high-level features/descriptors* into a single architecture, allowing to combine the power of both types of descriptors; and iv) its *extensibility* provided by the Description Definition Language which allows MPEG-7 to keep growing, to be extended to new application areas, to answer newly emerging needs and to integrate novel description tools. The MPEG-7 standard will be finalised by the end of 2001.

Although there are a few standardisation efforts under development, it is clear that MPEG-7 is the big standardisation challenge in the near future since it will be the first audiovisual representation standard with a target that is not reproduction for visualisation but description for retrieval and filtering. MPEG-7 shall form with MPEG-4 a powerful pair of standards, answering to most of the representation needs of advanced audiovisual applications. Their success will be deeply dependent on the capability to easily configure simple and adequate solutions for specific applications, avoiding the burdens resulting from the high number of applications and tools considered along the process.

4 FUTURE TRENDS ON VISUAL DATA REPRESENTATION

Although it is always difficult to predict the future, notably in very fast evolving areas, such as information technology in these days, there are some major trends that seem to emerge.

The above described standardisation landscape shows that most of the visual coding problems (as we see them today) are solved or are being solved¹ at least until the next technological jump arises. While minor refinements and improvements based on well-known technology are still possible, it is not expectable that they will bring significant changes.

It is however clear that standard audiovisual representation technology – coding and description - is not enough to deploy powerful multimedia applications. The technology in the standards is just the enabling factor to which non-normative technology has to be added to deploy advanced applications. Good MPEG-4 content and applications will require powerful tools for object-based rate control, error concealment, natural and synthetic object composition, object-based authoring, audiovisual segmentation, 3D modelling, etc. In the same way, powerful MPEG-7

¹ MPEG-4 did not yet address the problem of object-based multi-view coding, identified as a target at the beginning of the MPEG-4 process.

applications will require adequate technology for feature extraction, action classification, low-level to high-level information mapping, advanced querying, matching criteria, etc. All these technologies are non-normative: this means that they did not need to be mature at the time of the development of the standard but their performance will largely determine the success of the standards since they will determine the quality and functionality of the applications.

Analysis and Understanding

Much of the non-normative technology referred above is related to the analysis and understanding of the visual data to better code and describe it as well as to the analysis and understanding of the compressed data, and of the descriptions, to better and more easily use the content available. In other words, only with powerful analysis and understanding tools it will be possible to make good use of the tools made available by the standards. The better the visual content can be analysed and understood, the better it can be coded and described but also manipulated and used.

Moreover analysis and understanding will be more and more multi-modal and cross-modal, exploiting multisensory cues to improve performance and allow additional functionality. For example, it is possible to improve video story unit detection by using both video and audio information and it should be possible to look for a Pavarotti's picture using a Pavarotti's song.

Smart Sensors, Interfaces and Displays

Beside advanced processing and representation technologies, the deployment of advanced multimedia applications will be largely impacted by the developments in sensors, interfaces and displays. Smart sensors will ease the analysis and understanding tasks collecting more data from the real world, e.g. depth information for a visual scene. Pushing the limits, it is possible to imagine a future where analysis and understanding, e.g. for segmentation or scene description, will deal with environments where at least some of the objects will themselves spontaneously or on request inform about some of their characteristics: smart sensors will be complemented with smart objects. Also interfaces shall allow a more natural and powerful relation of the user with the content, e.g. navigation and interaction within virtual multimedia worlds. Finally, advanced multisensory high resolution 'displays' will allow creating fully immersive environments in which users will enjoy rich interactive experiences.

The Real-Virtual Continuum

Although MPEG-4 made a first big step towards the smooth integration of real and synthetic audiovisual data, there is still a long way to go before hybrid real-virtual worlds behave as a continuum. The trend to extend, complete, and substitute the reality by the

virtuality has strong motivations, still growing in the future, such as the shortage of natural resources and ecological awareness. The real-virtual continuum will be present in augmented worlds, fully virtual or fusing real and virtual, with high degrees of realism and interaction providing a powerful sensation of telepresence. For example, a big neutral room may become in the same day a sports pavilion, a concert hall and a meeting place with all the necessary equipment, just by means of virtual decoration, saving huge amounts of materials and human resources. The achievement of the real-virtual continuum will rely on many interdisciplinary areas such as audiovisual processing and representation, smart sensors, advanced (very likely wearable) displays and powerful interfaces.

5 FINAL REMARKS

After many years of technological developments in complementary areas, now converging and synergising, some elements of the multimedia puzzle seem to be in place. However other elements still require significant research and development efforts. It will only then be possible, for example to navigate in high quality virtual environments, transparently integrating natural and synthetic content, interacting with perfect representations of humans, animals or objects to perform the tasks relevant for the application in question. These experiences may be further enriched by integrating other sensory cues until now not exploited. Beside the typical constraints related to cost and performance, new dimensions such as intellectual property protection and ethical issues will play a major role in this hybrid future.

REFERENCES

- [1] F. Pereira, "MPEG-4: Why, What, How and When?", Tutorial Issue on the MPEG-4 Standard, Signal Processing: Image Communication, vol. 15, n° 4-5, December 1999
- [2] Gisle Bjontegaard (editor), "H.26L Test Model Long Term, number 3 (TML-3)", Doc. Q15-J-08, ITU-T Study Group 16, March 2000
- [3] MPEG Video Group, "MPEG-4 Visual – Proposed Draft Amendment (PDAM4), Doc. ISO/MPEG N3315, MPEG Noordwijkerhout meeting, March 2000
- [4] JPEG Requirements AHG, "JPEG2000 Requirements and Profiles, version 6.1", Doc. ISO/JPEG N1565, December 1999
- [5] JPEG, "JPEG 2000 FCD", Doc. ISO/JPEG N1646R, March 2000
- [6] MPEG Requirements Group, "MPEG-7 Overview", Doc. ISO/MPEG N3349, MPEG Noordwijkerhout meeting, March 2000